

VARICOSE VEIN TREATMENT: ARE NATURAL REMEDIES HELP ELIMINATING THEM?

Varicose veins are a result of weakened veins. Veins can get feeble because of basic things like folding one's legs or standing too long on a regular premise. Different elements that can impact the advancement of varicose veins are family ancestry, obesity, and pregnancy. If the ugly veins are bothering you, get [vein treatments near me](#).

Veins are the freeways that carry deoxygenated blood from the lower part of your body to the heart. When the vein walls become weak, they fail to transport the blood to the heart. As a result, blood starts pooling making veins' size bigger and swollen. Moreover, it causes the veins to become swollen, painful, and unsightly. Consult a **vein doctor near me in San Diego**, to get relief from them permanently.

What can be done?

There are many temporary treatments suggested by a **vein specialist near me in San Diego** that help relieve the symptoms of varicose veins. These procedures entail elevating one's legs, using anti-inflammatory medicine, and carrying specially designed hosiery that

compresses the legs. These **varicose vein treatments near me in San Diego** however are temporary and do not correct the actual problem.

Other than that there are some natural **vein treatments in California** that effectively ease the symptoms of varicose veins:

Apple Cider Vinegar:

It's a natural body cleansing product that improves blood flow and circulation. When you apply the vinegar, the blood starts flowing naturally thus decreasing the heaviness and swelling of the veins otherwise **get vein treatment la Jolla from a vein specialist in San Jose**.

You should apply undiluted vinegar on your skin and then gently massage the area. For ideal results, you should apply the vinegar two times a day, for a period of a few months.

In addition to applying the vinegar, it's also recommended that you drink it. Here you should add two teaspoons of apple cider vinegar to a glass of water and stir well. You should then drink it twice a day. For ideal results, you should drink the mixture for at least one month.

Grape Seeds:

Grape seeds are loaded with Vitamin E, linoleic acid, and flavonoids. These compounds aid in strengthening the blood veins and also kill free radicals that might be harmful to the veins. You should chew the seeds or make powder from the seeds. If you have some money you can purchase the grape seed supplements in your local store.

While the seeds are of great benefit to you, you should avoid them if you are pregnant or breastfeeding. You should also avoid them if you are taking blood thinners.

Olive Oil:

Having massages with olive oil enhance blood circulation leading to a reduction in pain and inflammation. You should blend equal amounts of vitamin E and olive oil and heat it slightly. You may use it to massage affected veins for a few minutes. For excellent outcomes, you should massage the oil minimum of two times a day up to a period of two months.

You can also mix two teaspoons of warm olive oil and four drops of cypress oil and use it to massage yourself.

Butcher's Broom:

It contains Ruscogenins that aid in reducing inflammation and vein constriction. You should take 100 mg of the supplement three times a day. While the herb is very effective in its working, you should avoid taking it without first consulting your doctor. This is particularly important if you are suffering from high blood pressure or benign prostate hyperplasia.

If you don't find these natural [varicose vein treatment](#) helpful, consult a **vein doctor near me in San Jose** immediately.